

THE FAILURE MECHANISM IN MONOFILAMENT-REINFORCED TITANIUM UNDER AXIAL COMPRESSION

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SUMMARY: Experiments have been carried out in which titanium reinforced with SiC monofilaments has been subjected to compressive loading parallel to the fibre axis. Apparent strengths of about 3 GPa have been obtained. It has been established that extensive matrix plasticity precedes failure during these tests. Calculations and strain gauge measurements suggest that failure may have been precipitated in these tests by inelastic long range buckling of the specimen. This is troublesome in view of the limited availability of material which is sufficiently thick to avoid the problem. Tests were therefore carried out to measure the *in situ* compressive strength of monofilaments located near the compression surface of a beam subjected to bending. Preliminary work has given an upper bound on this strength of about 8-9 GPa. Such stresses would be generated in a typical composite under an applied axial compressive stress of less than 4 GPa. This is much less than predicted strengths obtained using the concept commonly applied to polymer composites that failure occurs by shear yielding of the matrix on planes parallel to the fibre axis. It is therefore proposed that compressive failure of the fibres will often limit the strength of this class of material.

KEYWORDS: MMC, titanium matrix, compressive loading, kinking, buckling

INTRODUCTION

Most models for compressive failure of long-fibre composites focus on shear yielding of the matrix parallel to the fibre axis, which occurs more readily when there is significant misalignment between this direction and the loading axis. Argon[1] proposed that the axial compressive strength of the composite, σ_{c*} , can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{c*} = \frac{k}{\phi} \quad (1)$$

where k is the matrix shear yield stress and ϕ is the angle between the loading axis and the (local) fibre axis. For perfectly aligned fibres ($\phi=0^\circ$), Rosen[2] proposed that the strength should be given by

$$\sigma_{c*} = \frac{G_m}{(1-f)} \quad (2)$$

where G_m is the matrix shear modulus and f is the fibre volume fraction. In effect, these two models were combined by Budiansky and Fleck[3], who proposed that

$$\sigma_{c^*} = \frac{k}{(\gamma_Y (1-f) + \phi)} \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_Y = k / G_m$. This gives predictions tending to those of Rosen and Argon in the limits of low and high misalignments respectively.

Both the Argon and Budiansky and Fleck models centre on a failure mechanism in which a localised band of rotated fibres forms across the entire specimen width as the surrounding matrix yields in shear, i.e. the formation of a "kink-band". This failure stress will subsequently be referred to as the kinking stress. In contrast, the Rosen limit to compressive strength refers not to localised failure, but to global instability of the entire matrix and fibre assembly, as an alternative to kinking. It should be noted that for any given material, the Rosen limit is usually at least an order of magnitude larger than the kinking stress, unless the misalignment is taken to be extremely small.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Material And Specimen Preparation

The composite material, consisting of 36 vol% SiC monofilament (SM1240) in a matrix of Ti-6Al-4V, was prepared by DRA, using the foil-fibre-foil hot pressing technique[4]. The work described here was carried out using material supplied in the form of 12-ply plate, having a thickness of 2.0 mm. In addition to this composite material, mechanical testing was also carried out on unreinforced material in the form of 2 mm thick rolled sheet. Specimens for metallographic examination and mechanical testing were cut from this plate using electro-discharge machining, followed where appropriate by mechanical polishing.

Characterisation of Fibre Alignment

As reported in a previous publication[5], maximum fibre misalignment values were obtained experimentally using the method of Yurgartis[6]. Briefly, this involves taking accurate metallographic sections at low angles to the specimen loading axis and measuring the aspect ratios of the individual fibre profiles produced. These values were then transformed into angular misalignments with respect to the loading axis. Plotting the individual results on a histogram revealed that there was a spread of misalignments (around zero) of $\Delta\phi = \pm 2.0^\circ$.

Mechanical Testing

Compression testing was carried out on specimens with dimensions of $75 \times 10.0 \times 2.0$ mm and $75 \times 5.0 \times 2.0$ mm. These were cut with the long axis parallel to the edge of the original plate and hence to the nominal axis of fibre alignment. Strain gauge rosettes were attached to the centres of both the large faces, in order to monitor compressive strain, Poisson ratio and specimen bending. The specimens were held in two pairs of hydraulic grips, with a closing force of 30 kN. The grips were machined from low alloy steel, which was then hardened. One of the mating surfaces of each pair had a rectangular recess with dimensions of either

31.5 × 10 × 1.8 mm, or 30.0 × 5 × 1.8 mm, within which the specimen was located, and the other had a flat surface. Thus, the gauge lengths of the 5.0 mm specimens were about 13 mm, and those of the 10.0 mm specimens were about 11.5 mm. These are sufficiently short to avoid full-column elastic Euler buckling. The surfaces of the grips to be in contact with the specimen were all grit blasted to improve the transfer of shear load. Testing was carried out under displacement control, at a strain rate of 3 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Elastic and Plastic Deformation

A typical stress-strain plot is shown in Fig.1(a). Data are presented for the axial strain on both sides of the specimen. These coincide closely up until about 7 millistrain, when they slowly bifurcate prior to final failure. Also shown, in Fig.1(b), is a plot of the Poisson ratio against axial strain, for one of the two sides. (The 1, 2 and 3 directions correspond to the fibre axis, the in-plane transverse direction and the through-thickness transverse direction, normal to the plane of the titanium foils.) It can be seen in Fig.1(a) that the specimen experiences macroscopic plastic deformation at compressive strains above about 12 millistrain (1.2%). This is confirmed by the Poisson plot (Fig.1(b)), which shows a noticeable rise, associated with global matrix plasticity, at strains about 10 millistrain (1.0%). Clearly, a significant amount of plastic flow occurs before final failure.

Fig.1: Data from a typical mechanical test. (a) Stress-strain plots, obtained using outputs from the load cell and from the two axial strain gauges on either side of the specimen, and (b) a Poisson plot, using outputs from the axial and transverse strain gauges on one side of the specimen.

Table 1: Measured and calculated elastic constants and yielding / failure data for the composite.

Source	Property	Material		
		Ti-6-4	SiC monofilament	Ti-6-4 / 36% SiC
Measured (av. of 3 tests)	E_1 (GPa)	-	-	211
	ν_{31}	-	-	0.30
	σ_{1AY} (GPa)	0.90	-	2.10
	σ_{1A^*} (GPa)	-	-	2.90
Estimated	ΔT (K)	-	-	-500 [†]
Handbook Data or Calculated (After Li[7])	E_1 (GPa)	115	409	225
	ν_{31}	0.36	0.20	0.30
	G_{21}	42.3	-	63.4
	α_1 (K ⁻¹)	9.0×10^{-6}	4.0×10^{-6}	5.82×10^{-6}
	$\sigma_{1m\Delta T}$ (GPa)	-	-	0.243
	$\sigma_{3m\Delta T}$ (GPa)	-	-	0.083
	$\sigma_{1f\Delta T}$ (GPa)	-	-	-0.430
	σ_{1AY} (GPa)	0.9	-	2.06
E_T (GPa)	-	-	97.3	
	E_T (GPa)	-	-	~130

[†] The actual temperature drop during processing is significantly greater than this, but some creep and plastic flow might be expected during cooling, so that the effective ΔT value represented by the residual stresses is reduced.

Some simple calculations can be made concerning both elastic and plastic regimes. For example, the Eshelby method[8] can be used to calculate the elastic constants and also to treat the onset of plastic flow. This can be done by evaluating the volume-averaged matrix stresses under a given applied stress, taking account of residual thermal stresses, and applying a suitable yield criterion. In the present case, the von Mises criterion was used.

The Eshelby method can also be used to predict the maximum work-hardening rate expected on the basis of load transfer to the fibres after yielding occurs, assuming that the matrix itself does not work-harden, (a reasonable assumption for Ti-6Al-4V). Results from these operations are presented in Table 1. It can be seen that there is good agreement between measured and calculated values for both the elastic constants and for the applied compressive stress at the onset of yielding.

Failure

As previously reported[5], some specimens failed by the formation of a type of kink band, as is consistent with the modelling approach of Argon. However, when the Argon formula for prediction of the failure stress is applied, the agreement with experiment is very poor. This remains true when developments of the approach, such as that of Budiansky & Fleck, are applied. This is illustrated by Fig.2, which shows a plot of failure stress (normalised by the matrix shear yield stress, $k = 0.450$ GPa) as a function of fibre misalignment angle, ϕ . On this plot, various data are shown from previous work on polymer composites, together with results from the current work. It can be seen that, while agreement between theory and experiment

appears good for many polymer composites, the observed strengths are well below those predicted for these MMCs. Indeed, if the Argon predictions were to be fulfilled for this material, even assuming the value of ϕ could be as high as 2° , then the kinking stress would be about 12.9 GPa; it would be very surprising if such high strengths could be achieved. Conversely, the measured compressive strength of about 2.9 GPa corresponds to a ϕ value of about 10° , which is quite inconsistent with microstructural observations.

Fig.2: Experimental strength data, as a function of fibre misalignment, from the current work and from previous studies on polymer-based composites[9-11], together with predictions from the Argon[1] (eqn.(1)) and Budiansky & Fleck[3] (eqn.(3)) models. The latter is shown for values of f and γ typical of polymer- and metal-based long fibre composites.

For monofilament-reinforced metals, the high matrix shear yield stress and/or the good fibre alignment elevate the kinking stress above the level at which alternative failure mechanisms are likely to occur. (Note that the Rosen limit for our MMC material is 66.1 GPa, which is quite impossible).

Mechanical tests were also performed on unreinforced (matrix-only) specimens having the same dimensions as the composite. It was found that a form of inelastic buckling failure occurred in all cases. After yielding at around 0.9 GPa, limiting loads of ~ 1.0 GPa were approached, as the specimen became increasingly deformed. Fig.3 shows the longitudinal profile of a matrix-only specimen after loading. (The figure has been foreshortened by a factor of 2.5 in the axial direction in order to accentuate the curvature.) It is evident that considerable plastic deformation has occurred upon buckling.

Fig.3: Profile of matrix-only specimen after compressive loading. (Note that this image has been artificially compressed in the loading direction to accentuate the specimen curvature which has occurred.) The numbered arrows refer to the positions of the strain gauges in Fig.4.

In view of this result, it was decided to repeat some of the tests on reinforced specimens, in order to ascertain whether or not they too adopt similarly buckled shapes prior to failure. As the suspected buckling mode would not be detected via gauges placed in the middle of the gauge length, axial strain gauges were placed at the quarter-length points on both sides. Fig.4 shows the axial strains measured at these four points during compressive loading. These strains are indeed consistent with the buckled configuration seen in the unreinforced specimens. It is worth noting that the lateral deflections of the specimen producing these strains would be undetectable by eye.

Fig.4: Compressive stress vs. axial strains for 5.0 mm wide specimen, with strain gauges placed at the quarter-length points, on both sides of the specimen. Note that the curvatures at the ends of the gauge length are approximately equal and are in opposite senses.

PREDICTION OF MACROSCOPIC BUCKLING LOADS

Elastic Case

The simplest approach to predicting a macroscopic buckling instability in an axially compressed column is due to Euler[12]. In the fully elastic regime, the buckling load P_c can be related to the gauge length of the sample, the moment of inertia in the plane of buckling (I) and the axial modulus (E).

$$P_c = \frac{C\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \quad (4)$$

where, for a rectangular column, $I = bh^3/12$ and C is a constant related to the degree of clamping provided by the loading fixture. The value of C ranges from 1 (when the clamping is such that the tangents to the curves at the ends of the column are constrained to remain parallel with the loading axis, but the ends themselves may translate sideways during loading) to 4 (where the ends are neither allowed to rotate or translate relative to the loading axis). The buckled profiles of the matrix-only specimens are consistent with the condition corresponding to $C = 1$, as are the strain data for the reinforced specimen.

The elastic buckling stress σ_c^{el} is therefore given by

$$\sigma_c^{el} = \frac{P}{A} = \frac{C\pi^2 EI}{(L/r)^2} = \frac{C\pi^2 E}{s^2} \quad (5)$$

where the radius of gyration is given by $r = \sqrt{I/A}$ and the slenderness ratio by $s = L/r$. The critical slenderness ratio s_c is the value of s below which the fully elastic (Euler) treatment becomes inappropriate, i.e. for $s < s_c$ then $\sigma_Y < \sigma_c^{el}$.

From Eqn.(5), the value of s_c is therefore given by

$$s_c = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 C E}{\sigma_Y}} \quad (6)$$

For the present case, using the elastic constants from Table 1, along with the measured composite yield stress (σ_{Yc}) of 2.1 GPa and the most likely clamping condition ($C = 1$), gives $s_c = 30$. These specimens had slenderness ratios varying from 20.0 to 22.5, so it would be expected that inelastic (i.e. plastic) buckling would occur well before elastic buckling. (It follows that reducing the gauge length sufficiently to prevent Euler buckling was inadequate to prevent plastic buckling in this case).

Inelastic Case

A suitable approach to predicting the lowest stress at which an inelastic material will buckle is given by Shanley[13]. In his analysis, the inelastic buckling criterion is very similar to the Euler equation (Eqn.(4)), but with the elastic modulus E replaced by the instantaneous tangent modulus E_T , where E_T is given by $\partial\sigma/\partial\varepsilon$ evaluated at the buckling load. The Shanley formula therefore gives the inelastic buckling stress (σ_c^{in}) as

$$\sigma_c^{\text{in}} = \frac{C\pi^2 ET}{s^2} \quad (7)$$

Values for E_T taken from the literature[7] (data from tensile tests on the same material - see Table 1) were used to calculate σ_c^{in} for various slenderness ratios. These are plotted, along with the elastic (Euler) predictions, in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Experimental strength data as a function of slenderness ratio, s with the predictions based on macroscopic specimen buckling, either elastic or inelastic (Eqns.(5), (7) and (8)).

Also plotted on the figure are inelastic buckling predictions that have been corrected for shear deformation, according to Eqn.(8), below[14], where G_{21} has been evaluated using the Eshelby method (see Table 1).

$$\sigma_c^{\text{in,corr}} = \frac{\sigma_c^{\text{in}}}{1 + \frac{1.2 \sigma_c^{\text{in}}}{G_{21}}} \quad (8)$$

Although this is generally a small correction, it becomes significant at low slenderness ratios (i.e. short, stubby beams) and is therefore included for completeness. It may also be argued that, since the axial modulus of the composite approaches E_T with increasing plastic strain, the shear modulus should be reduced (making the correction more significant) so Eqn.(8) is also plotted using a 50% reduced shear modulus as an attempt to incorporate this effect.

Several points can be made regarding this figure.

- (a) Experimental failure strengths are of the same magnitude as predicted inelastic buckling stresses, and are much closer than those predicted on the basis of a fibre kinking mechanism.

- (b) Experimental failure strengths are 36% larger for 5 mm wide specimens, even though they are slightly more slender than 10 mm wide specimens. This may be due to the grips providing less effective clamping at the higher loads attained with wider specimens (i.e. $C < 1$, allowing the specimen ends to rotate).
- (c) Inelastic buckling may be much more important in MMCs than in PMCs due to their more pronounced inelastic behaviour prior to compressive failure. Also, PMC specimens can be produced of sufficiently low slenderness ratios to preclude even inelastic buckling effects.
- (d) Much squatter specimens are required to avoid inelastic buckling in these MMC compression specimens, either through production of thicker section material (which may be prohibitively expensive or technically difficult) or via hotpress diffusion bonding of several as-consolidated panels (which will impose a further heat-treatment on the material).

ALTERNATIVE SPECIMEN GEOMETRY FOR COMPRESSION TESTING

A specimen geometry allowing large axial compressive loads to be imposed on a single layer of reinforcing fibres, without encountering difficulties due to global specimen instability, is one in which the fibres are located on the compression side of a beam. This has been suggested previously for this type of testing[15]. A single fibre layer was consolidated between matrix foils to produce a reinforced "monosheet". This monosheet was then diffusion bonded to a stack of Ti-6Al-4V plates, in order to form a deep beam. This beam was then loaded in 4-point flexure. During the test, axial strains at the surface of the beam were measured by using a strain gauge, as shown in Fig.6. According to the plastic theory of deep beams, it is relatively easy to show[16] that the strains actually experienced by the sub-surface fibres are similar to the measured surface strains, to within a few %. Bending of the fibres is minimised by using a deep beam, with the fibres well away from the neutral axis. In fact, the minimum bend radius to which these fibres were exposed during this test was about 150 mm, which may be compared with a reported value necessary to cause failure of about 10 mm.

The main objective of this testing was to establish the compressive strength of the reinforcing fibres themselves, when they undergo brittle fracture within the plastically deforming matrix. Preliminary tests have been aimed at establishing an upper bound to this strength by extracting fibres from the matrix before and after subjecting the monosheet to a specified compressive strain. Fibres were extracted by using a strong etch of 25 % HF acid in water to dissolve the surrounding matrix. Fig.7 shows such extracted fibres, the loaded specimen in this case having been subjected to a strain of 2%. It is clear that this strain was sufficient to cause extensive compressive failure. The absence of significant damage to the fibres from the unloaded specimen confirms that damage did not arise during material preparation or matrix dissolution.

Fig.6: Specimen construction and dimensions for compression testing by flexure.

Fig.7: Photographs of extracted fibres from specimens subjected to (a) no loading and (b) bending so that the compressive surface was subjected to a strain of 2.0%.

By completing a series of tests, at different compressive strains, it was found that a strain of 1.6 % was sufficient to promote significant fibre fracture. This corresponds to an applied axial compressive stress of 6.5 GPa. The total axial stress on the fibres is higher than this due to the presence of thermal residual stresses. The axial thermal residual stress was calculated as -1.75 GPa, using $\Delta T = -900$ K from the diffusion bonding temperature and an overall fibre volume fraction of 1.5 %, so that the total axial compressive stress in the fibres was ~ 8.3 GPa. This represents an upper bound on the fibre compressive strength. This figure may be compared with typical *in situ* tensile strengths exhibited by these fibres of about 3-4 GPa.

FIBRE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND FAILURE

Although the fibre compressive strength measured via beam-bending is an upper limit, it is still well below the compressive stress expected in the fibres at the onset of kinking, according to either the Argon or Budiansky and Fleck models. Reading directly from the graph of Fig.2, the kinking stress predicted for the MMC material being studied here is 12.9 GPa. At these stress levels, even assuming elastic load sharing between matrix and fibres, the axial compressive stress in the fibres would be about 23.4 GPa; taking plasticity into account would substantially increase this figure. It therefore seems paradoxical that some of the specimens clearly failed in a manner similar to kinking. However, it seems likely that such features arose after instabilities had been produced by fibre fracture, which allowed gross local plastic deformation of the type seen during kinking.

From a knowledge of the compressive strength of the fibres, is possible to predict the compressive strength of the composite based on a fibre failure criterion. Assuming a fibre compressive failure strain of 1.6 %, the matrix will already be fully plastic at this stage, so a simple equal strain condition can be invoked to predict the failure stress.

$$\sigma_{c*} = f\sigma_{f*} + (1-f)\sigma_{Ym} \quad (9)$$

When appropriate values are inserted into this equation, $\sigma_{c*} \approx 3.6$ GPa is obtained as an upper limit on the composite compressive strength. This is only slightly greater than observed failure values obtained hitherto of about 2.9 GPa., which suggests that the true strength might be measurable by conventional compressive testing of composite material, providing minor steps can be taken to reduce further the danger of inelastic buckling. Further work of this type is required before it can be confirmed that a completely different failure criterion is appropriate for prediction of the compressive strength of such MMCs than has been used hitherto for polymer composites.

CONCLUSIONS

1. MMC material composed of Ti-6Al-4V reinforced with SiC monofilaments has been tested in compression. Apparent failure stresses of about 3 GPa have been obtained.
2. Such strength levels are substantially below those predicted on the basis of established theories of compressive strength, based on failure occurring when the matrix undergoes shear yielding on planes parallel to the fibre axis. Such predictions give rise to extremely high values (>10 GPa) for these materials, as a consequence of the excellent fibre alignment they exhibit and the high matrix yield stress.
3. It has been established that, although the specimen dimensions employed were such as to ensure that elastic (Euler) buckling could not occur, it is probable that failure was initiated by inelastic long range buckling. This is consistent with measurements made during loading which confirmed that matrix plasticity was well developed by the time that failure occurred.
4. While the measured strength values are thus invalid, it is suspected that these composites will not in fact sustain appreciably higher stresses. This postulate is based on preliminary measurements of the compressive failure strength of the monofilaments, undertaken by incorporating them into the compressive face of a beam loaded in bending. These experiments have tentatively established an upper bound on the compressive strength of these monofilaments, when located within this matrix, of about 8.6 GPa. It follows that the composites would fail, by compressive failure of the fibres, at applied stresses of the order of 3.7 GPa.

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